

*Innovative Large-Scale
Production of Affordable Clean
Burning Solid Biofuel and
Water in Southern Africa*

**VERIFIED VIABLE SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS
MODELS FOR THE SOLID BIOFUEL
COMMERCIALISATION**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

Executive summary

The EU-funded Horizon2020 SteamBioAfrica (SBA) project demonstrates the use of superheated steam (SHS) technology to convert unwanted biomass (encroacher bush) into a clean-burning solid biofuel, creating value from waste.

The project produces SBA solid biofuel using an SHS plant installed at the Cheetah Conservation Fund (CCF) in Otjiwarongo, Namibia. This biofuel is offered as an alternative to firewood and charcoal in local markets across Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa.

Key advantages of SBA solid biofuel include its **reduced smoke emissions**, making it ideal for indoor cooking and heating with **minimal health risks**. Additionally, its **dry and hydrophobic properties** ensure **easy handling, storage, and quick burning**. Furthermore, the sustainability of the biofuel is a significant benefit, as the biomass is harvested sustainably, **contributes to land restoration, and reduces greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions** from cooking and heating.

The primary objective of Work Package 10 (WP10) within the SBA project is to facilitate the wide-scale commercialisation of clean-burning SBA solid biofuel. This report, Deliverable 10.4, focuses on the downstream value chain, where the participation of retail Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) is crucial.

As part of WP10, the SBA project aims to identify innovative and viable sustainable business models suitable for biomass MSMEs operating downstream in the value chains of the three target countries. The goal is to enable these MSMEs to adopt and sell the clean-burning solid biofuel. Given their extensive presence and proximity to household consumers, biomass MSMEs are well-positioned to promote the new solid biofuel and facilitate its acceptance among consumers.

This report recommends four business models for the commercialisation of the new solid biofuel:

- **Cash and carry:** Customers purchase SBA solid biofuel directly from sellers, suitable for both formal and informal businesses, with or without delivery services.
- **Product bundling:** Combines SBA solid biofuel with complementary products (e.g., cookstoves, firewood/charcoal) to offer added value and convenience, applicable to large retailers and smaller vendors with financial capacity.
- **Distributor model:** Uses intermediaries to distribute SBA solid biofuel to retail outlets, institutions, and end-users, leveraging networks for market reach and scalability.
- **E-commerce model:** Sells SBA solid biofuel directly to consumers via online platforms, offering convenience and accessibility with included delivery services.

These models were tested and verified through product sales trials conducted in Windhoek and Gaborone between May and June 2024.

The report also provides an overview of **major competing solid biofuel sources**, market trends and demand analysis, and touches on the regulatory framework governing solid biofuels. It identifies both **formal** (large and small retailers, gas stations) and **informal** (kiosks, roadside vendors) businesses as potential implementers of the recommended models. Finally, the report reviews **financing instruments and investment options to support the implementation of the selected business models**.

Conclusions

This report contributes to WP10 with the primary objective of validating business models (**Business model #1 and Business Model #2**) which were identified in SBA D9.3 report as relevant for commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel and, based on the validation, **proposes novel sustainable and viable business models** that are suitable for MSMEs, particularly those in the downstream of the biomass value chains in Southern Africa. It identifies four business models mentioned above that are deemed suitable for SBA solid biofuel commercialisation.

The business models are tailored for downstream value chain participants engaged in distribution, retail, and consumption. **Three of these models were tested and validated** during the project's product sales trials, based on **feedback and engagement with stakeholders**. Additionally, an e-commerce model is proposed for future consideration by biomass MSMEs

Each model was assessed using a SWOT analysis to identify its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, providing a comprehensive evaluation framework. Based on this assessment, four business models are proposed and presented using a sustainable business model canvas, as they are deemed viable and sustainable for MSMEs to consider.

Furthermore:

- **Strategic partnerships** with various actors across the value chain were found to be **crucial for the commercialisation of the solid biofuel**. Successfully bringing this new solid biofuel to market will require the involvement of multiple stakeholders in local biomass value chains.
- The product sales trial highlighted the **need for optimisation of the SBA solid biofuel to enhance its market competitiveness**. Specifically, customers suggested increasing the particle size (from P30 to P100) and extending its burn time as two key areas for improvement.

The findings and business models presented in this report will be useful for downstream MSMEs seeking to diversify their income streams by incorporating clean-burning solid biofuel into their product portfolios. These insights will enable MSMEs to not only meet environmental goals but also broaden their revenue streams, enhancing their competitiveness in a rapidly evolving market landscape. This strategic initiative ensures sustainable growth and resilience in the part of the MSMEs in the face of changing consumer preferences and regulatory frameworks.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
MSMEs	Micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises
SBA	SteamBioAfrica
SHS	Superheated steam
NAM	Namibia
BOT	Botswana
BM	Business model
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer

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Overview

1.1.1 Introduction

Work Package 10 (WP10) of the EU Horizon 2020 SteamBioAfrica (SBA) project aims to identify and improve existing biomass value chains to facilitate large-scale commercialisation of the proposed SBA solid biofuel product.

This Deliverable 10.4 (Verified Viable Sustainable Business Models for the Solid Biofuel Commercialisation) report builds on and complements three other deliverables within the SBA project: D10.1 (A Value Chain Mapping Report Covering the Three Target Countries), D9.3 (Identified Viable Business Models and Green Financing Instruments), and D10.5 (Innovative MSME Financing Toolbox).

Deliverable 10.1 focused on the downstream value chains of cooking and heating energy sources such as charcoal and firewood, including distribution, retail, and consumption stages. It assessed the existing value chains of solid energy sources for cooking and heating in the project's three target countries: Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa. The end goal of the analysis was to verify and propose viable and innovative business models that biomass MSMEs could adopt when introducing the new clean-burning solid biofuel to local markets. This necessitated understanding supply- and demand-side trends in the three countries and matching them with potentially effective marketing strategies, distribution channels, and pricing approaches—key elements of a business model.

The Deliverable D9.3 report, submitted by the Botswana Institute for Technology Research and Innovation (BITRI), sought to identify viable business models in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa, as well as financing tools conducive to the commercialisation of the solid biofuel upon and following the completion of the SBA project. The report outlined several viable business models deemed feasible and well-suited for deployment by MSMEs, including wholesalers, distributors, and retailers. The identification of business models aimed to benefit local MSMEs, often located within communities, by stimulating new and sustainable revenue streams, especially in rural areas.

This Deliverable 10.4 report builds on and adds to the three above-mentioned key deliverables, particularly to test and validate the identified business models (BMs) in D9.3, which are suitable for downstream MSMEs. In the final section (Chapter 7), the report provides a brief overview of the financing and investment options required for the commercial success of SBA Biofuel, setting the stage for further discussion in Deliverable D10.5 (2024).

1.1.2 Background

The SteamBioAfrica (SBA) project, launched in September 2021, is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme and implemented in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. With 15 partners from Europe and Africa, the project addresses bush encroachment by utilising innovative superheated steam (SHS) technology. This technology converts biomass from encroaching bush and invasive plants into a clean-burning solid biofuel (SBA solid biofuel), along with water and other chemical by-products. The project aims to tackle environmental issues such as water scarcity, sustainable land restoration, and climate change mitigation, while indirectly addressing societal issues like unemployment and promoting social inclusion.

The clean biomass energy market in southern Africa is still nascent (Adedeji et al., 2020). Traditional biomass energy products, which adversely impact health and the environment, dominate the African energy market, particularly among lower-income populations (Basso et al., 2021). Developing a market for clean, affordable biomass energy is crucial. Work Package 10 (WP10) focuses on downstream businesses to create a thriving SHS biomass industry that is socially and environmentally sustainable. The SBA solid biofuel, a new product, presents an opportunity to be promoted through innovative and viable business models.

Successful commercialisation and widespread adoption of SBA solid biofuel are expected to enhance access to high-value, clean, secure, and affordable renewable energy in the target countries. Local communities will benefit from health advantages and new, sustainable revenue streams, especially in peri-urban and rural contexts. Developing business models within the biomass sector can improve access to cleaner energy, increase market competitiveness, and potentially lower solid biofuel prices. According to the D10.1 report, rural areas in the three countries have poor electrical energy distribution, with many people still relying on traditional fuels like firewood and charcoal. Identifying, testing, and verifying business models for MSMEs distributing biomass fuels can lead to broader consumer reach, sustainable bush harvesting, new employment opportunities, and improved energy access for the rural poor.

Innovative and viable business models for biomass MSMEs will facilitate the replication of SHS technology in the region. Effective uptake of these models requires robust product optimisation and pretesting, involving strategies that appeal to potential users.

Objectives of the Report

This report aims to test and validate business models for downstream biomass value chains identified in Report D9.3 (BITRI, 2023), as part of WP10's objective to promote large-scale, equitable economic benefits and job creation in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa through broad product uptake and consumer acceptance of the clean-burning solid biofuel. Specifically, the report will:

- Present a detailed analysis of each business model under consideration.
- Evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of each model based on predetermined criteria.
- Discuss the potential opportunities and risks associated with each business model.
- Recommend a set of verified business models that are viable.

Methodology and approach

1.1.3 Qualitative Methods

This report uses qualitative methods to analyse various business models relevant to the downstream segments of biomass value chains. The primary data sources include feedback from MSME participants in the Business Model Workshop Series conducted by the SBA project in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa between October 2023 and February 2024. These workshops provided valuable insights into the practical aspects and feasibility of different business models. Additionally, data was gathered from a biofuel sales trial, which offered real-world insights into market dynamics and consumer behavior. Furthermore, reviews of case

studies, relevant documents, and grey literature were conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of successful business models and best practices in the biomass sector.

Throughout the data collection process, ethical considerations were strictly adhered to, in line with EU and project guidelines. Particular attention was paid to ensuring informed consent from all participants and maintaining the confidentiality of the information gathered. This approach not only ensured the integrity of the data but also fostered trust and cooperation among the participants, leading to more accurate and insightful findings.

1.1.4 Product Sales Trial

The SBA project aimed to validate identified business models (BMs) and assess consumer acceptance of SBA solid biofuel through sales trials in Gaborone (Botswana) and Windhoek (Namibia). MSME sellers who had participated in SBA project activities, including baseline surveys in 2022, business-related training, and business model workshops (October 2023 – February 2024), were approached to trial the sale of SBA solid biofuel. Through the Namibian and Botswana project partners, N-Big and BITRI respectively, the project signed agreements with interested small sellers (MSMEs) – including kiosks, gas stations, and other vendors – providing them with a small batch of solid biofuel to sell to their existing customers (households and individual customers) during May and June 2024.

However, delays in commissioning the integrated SHS plant, as reported in the SteamBioAfrica D3.2 report, affected the timeline for WP5 activities focused on testing and optimising the solid biofuel. This resulted in a smaller-scale validation process and necessitated adjustments to the sales trial period, which consequently had a limited timeframe for collecting feedback, particularly from sellers. Given the limited timeframe and the significant demand for solid biofuels by household consumers, especially in rural and peri-urban areas, the project decided to undertake the biofuel sales trials in and around Windhoek (Namibia) and Gaborone (Botswana). According to the SBA Deliverable 10.1 report:

- South Africa has the highest grid access (81%) in Africa, with 87% of households having access to electricity, although 47% are considered energy poor.
- In Namibia, 53% and 46% of households use firewood for cooking and heating, respectively, with firewood being the dominant energy source in rural areas.
- In Botswana, access to electricity reaches 72% in urban areas and 57% in rural areas.

Data collection

As of June 15th, 2024, a total of 33 responses from household customers (26 from Namibia and 7 from Botswana) and 8 responses from small sellers (3 from Namibia and 5 from Botswana) in different locations had been collected. This data collection took place within a two-week period following the initial product launch in early May 2024.

Among the customer respondents, the gender ratio was 18 male to 15 female (Figure 1). Regarding age distribution, 13% were under 25 years old, 45% were between 25 and 45 years old, and 42% were over 45 years old (Figure 2). Out of the 28 customers who disclosed their location, only one lived in a rural area, five resided in peri-urban areas, and the rest were located in urban areas. In Windhoek, the three small sellers were located in shanty towns surrounding the city.

Figure 1: Gender of respondents in BOT and NAM

Figure 2: Age distribution of respondents in BOT and NAM

Most of the completed customer questionnaires (25 out of 33) were collected from small sellers, such as informal cooking vendors and kapana (grilled meat) sellers. Additional responses came from sales taking place in gas stations and supermarkets.

The use of sustainable business model canvas

For this study, we employed a sustainable business model canvas (Figure 3), which comprises 11 key elements, including value propositions, customer relationships, customer segments, channels, and revenue streams. In evaluating product sales performance and testing and validating business models (Chapter 5), the sales trial survey analysed several crucial aspects, such as product pricing, product information delivery, packaging, and product placement (the latter is detailed by BITRI in the independent D9.4 report).

At the outset, sellers in both Gaborone and Windhoek agreed to provide weekly feedback to the SBA project on the biofuel sales trials. To facilitate this, they were equipped with two sets of feedback questionnaires—one for the sellers themselves and another for their buyers or household consumers. This setup enabled the project to regularly monitor both **product sales performance** and **consumer acceptance of SBA solid biofuel**, critical for evaluating the viability of the identified business models.

Regarding pricing, N-Big and BITRI proposed a **price range** within which sellers were expected to market the solid biofuel. This range was informed by their assessment of market prices for firewood and charcoal, considering factors such as production costs, market demand, consumers’ willingness to pay, and competitive pricing against similar but less sustainable products in the region. Sellers were then responsible for reporting back to the project on the prices that customers were willing to pay, assisting in determining an acceptable and competitive price range for SBA solid biofuel in Botswana’s and Namibia’s markets.

During the sales trials, sellers targeted household consumers, distributing the product in 4-kg plastic bag packaging. Each bag included a product label sticker and an attached one-page product information sheet. The choice of plastic packaging was made for its transparency, ensuring that the solid biofuel was well-perceived visually by customers. According to N-Big and BITRI, this visibility was crucial as the product was new to local customers who needed to inspect it before purchase. The project also considered using more sustainable packaging, such as paper bags commonly used for selling charcoal in local supermarkets. This option may be revisited once the solid biofuel becomes widely recognised and has its brand image established in the market.

At the time of writing, data collection from the sales trials is still ongoing. However, due to delays mentioned earlier in this report affecting the rollout of the trials, comprehensive data for a thorough analysis and

validation of the identified business models (as detailed in the SBA D9.3 report by BITRI) was not available for this report. Nevertheless, the SBA project intends to publish the most up-to-date results of the sales trials on its website and other platforms. The report will also be distributed to relevant stakeholders, including biomass-based enterprises in the three countries and policymakers who have shown interest in the solid biofuel.

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

Figure 3: Sustainable Business Model Canvas

1.1.5 Namibia

In Windhoek, five **informal sellers**, including **kiosks and vendors** who had participated in the SBA project’s business-related training and business model workshops, expressed interest in testing the sale of the solid biofuel. However, only three of them completed the feedback questionnaire, while another seller reported no sales. These sellers operated in informal settlements around Windhoek, where a need for an alternative and cleaner fuel had been identified during the project's baseline survey (see also D10.1 report).

During the approximately four-week sales trial period, **a total of 48 bags** of the solid biofuel, pre-packaged in 4-kg plastic bags, were distributed. By the time of finalising this report, **30 bags had been sold** at prices ranging from N\$ 8.75 to 11.25 per kg (EUR 0.45 - 0.58 per kg). This price range was **slightly lower than the average price of charcoal**, which was around N\$ 12.91 per kg (EUR 0.64 per kg). **By undercutting the price of charcoal** (which is higher than firewood) on the market, the **sellers aimed to attract household customers** to purchase and use the SBA solid biofuel. However, due to the small sample size, it is not possible to conclusively determine that the lower price was the key factor driving customer purchases.

Other factors motivating households to buy the solid biofuel could include **personal contacts** with the sellers (especially when they are regular customers of the shops), **accessible locations** of the vendors and shops (being situated close to or within the communities), and **interest in the new/alternative biofuel**. The product information listed several advantages of the solid biofuel, including its environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the project identified that an extended period of product sales trials would be vital to identify repeat customers. Currently, it is unclear if there were repeat purchases as customers became convinced of the solid biofuel's utility.

1.1.6 Botswana

In Gaborone, the SBA project identified **six sellers** interested in testing the solid biofuel by offering it to their household customers. These sellers included three **gas stations**, two **roadside vendors**, and one **shop**. By collaborating with these diverse seller types, the SBA project aimed to gain meaningful insights into the most effective marketing channels for the solid biofuel, as each group has different locations and customer bases.

It is noteworthy that the domestic user trial (under WP5.4) and the domestic market product placement strategy (under WP9.3) were conducted concurrently in Gaborone. This synchronisation was possible because BITRI (WP9 leader) obtained an optimised solid biofuel from the SHS plant in Otjiwarongo, Namibia, toward the end of April 2024. The shipment comprised several tons of solid biofuel for various project activities.

During the sales trial period, a total of **170 bags of the solid biofuel**, pre-packaged in 4-kg plastic bags, were distributed to the sellers. By the time of finalising this report, **35 bags had been sold** at prices ranging from BWP 5 to BWP 10 (EUR 0.34 – 0.69) per kg. Gas stations sold the most, with 32 bags, likely due to:

- Lower prices: The price range at gas stations was relatively lower than the average price of charcoal in Botswana, which was around BWP 7 (EUR 0.48) per kg.
- Accessible locations: Gas stations in Botswana often have small supermarkets selling various consumer goods. This convenience allows car owners to purchase solid biofuel alongside other items while refilling their vehicles.

BITRI, the Botswana project partner, observed that people who use firewood and charcoal frequently purchase these fuels at gas stations, highlighting the potential of this sales channel for the solid biofuel.

1.1.7 Results of the Sales Trials

Consumer Preferences

The majority of household respondents used the SBA solid biofuel primarily for **cooking**, with a few using it for home heating. While most found the product's performance **somewhat satisfactory**, particularly appreciating the **reduced smoke**, they noted that it **burns out too quickly compared to charcoal and firewood**. Some consumers mentioned the need to **mix it with other solid fuels** to reach the desired cooking temperature. Many suggested **increasing the size of the solid biofuel pieces** (from P30 to P100) to improve the user experience and extend burn time.

Additionally, more than half of the respondents **still preferred traditional firewood** due to the SBA solid biofuel's quick burning nature and higher price. Buyers in Namibia **recommended a price reduction** to better compete with more affordable and better-performing alternatives like firewood. However, in Botswana, where the solid biofuel was sold at a price cheaper than firewood by some sellers, there was no clear correlation between the lower price and higher sales.

Seller Preferences

Generally, sellers of the SBA solid biofuel appreciated the **ease of storage**. Compared to traditional solid biofuels (firewood, charcoal), many preferred the SBA solid biofuel as it is **cleaner (no black dust)** and comes in pre-packaged bags. The SBA solid biofuel is also **lighter**, making it **easier to transport and safer to handle**.

However, aside from one seller from Namibia, all remaining sellers reported difficulties in selling the solid biofuel. The key reason is that the **product is not well-known by the general consumers**. This highlights the need for product branding and promotion to drive consumer purchases.

Two sellers from Botswana revealed that they would **benchmark the buying and selling prices of SBA solid biofuel with fire lighters available in the market, rather than with charcoal**. This indicates the current utility of the solid biofuel, which is more suitable as a fire lighter since it burns quickly and is not yet suitable for cooking some traditional meals that require longer cooking times. Further product optimisation would be needed to offer the SBA solid biofuel as an alternative to charcoal, which is considered a "dirtier" fuel due to its association with GHG emissions (during production) and health issues (during indoor cooking and heating).

Policy and regulatory framework

Biomass energy remains crucial in many developing countries, necessitating improvements in its supply, use, and technology (Biggs, 2009). Global agreements such as the Paris Agreement and Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 push for universal access to sustainable energy, urging countries like Namibia, South Africa, and Botswana to pursue carbon neutrality and emission reductions (Maswabi et al., 2021, p. 2).

Intermediaries and donors play a pivotal role in promoting biofuels, addressing gaps where governments are hesitant. Fiscal measures such as tax exemptions for clean biomass-based fuels and formalising the charcoal sector are vital but often challenged by corruption. Trade policies, like import duty exemptions for biofuel equipment, are essential for business stability. Policy frameworks in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa require enhancements to combat energy poverty and social disparities, necessitating better coordination and licensing for solid biofuel distribution (SBA D10.3, 2022, p. 5).

To foster **sustainable bioenergy sector development**, clear policy frameworks incentivising adoption are crucial, considering economic, social, and environmental factors. Initiatives should assess job creation potential and engage private stakeholders, while cohesive energy policies among countries will support collective progress. Transparent biofuel practices will secure local support and stakeholder engagement (Jha & Schmidt, 2021, p. 12).

1.1.8 Botswana

Botswana, a middle-income country committed to economic growth and diversification, faces growing energy demand. The government's aspirations to achieve a "sustainable environment" necessitate the adoption of cleaner energy production options (Maswabi et al., 2021, p. 1). While Botswana has untapped potential in solar, wind, and hydropower, previous renewable energy projects have often failed due to poor quality and maintenance.

The country's Biofuel Guidelines largely overlook solid fuels, highlighting the need for a comprehensive framework that includes incentives and stakeholder engagement (Botswana Energy Regulatory Authority

[BERA], 2021). Support for the solid biofuel generated by the SteamBioAfrica project, through measures such as tax relief, innovative pricing, or subsidies (during the initial adoption stage), is crucial (SBA D10.3, 2022).

1.1.9 Namibia

Namibia, despite having sound institutions, has an underdeveloped bioenergy policy environment (Brüntrup et al., 2016). The country faces significant inequality in energy infrastructure between its wealthier South and poorer North (p. 5). However, it possesses substantial potential for bioenergy derived from encroaching bush, a major source of bioenergy and land degradation (p. 2). Proper management and policy support can leverage this potential for clean energy. The established Bush Management Strategy of Namibia provides a foundation for sustainable biofuel commercialisation (Ministry of Environment, Forestry and Tourism [Namibia], 2022).

Strengthening agricultural policies, labour regulations, and decision-making procedures is essential for coordinated land and resource governance and advancing bioenergy development. Environmental protection is strongly supported and constitutionally rooted in Namibia.

1.1.10 South Africa

Coal dominates South Africa's energy mix, hindering the development of renewable energy projects. Progress is further impeded by poor policy coordination, varying competencies at the municipal level, and **limited access to finance**. Consequently, despite the country's renewable energy potential, **low-income households** still often rely on inefficient biomass energy due to its affordability (SBA D10.3, 2022, p. 5). Addressing structural inequalities and affordability challenges is therefore critical.

Although the government committed to increasing biofuel production in 2007, large-scale procurement has not yet commenced (Henley & Fundira, 2019, p. 255). Current biofuel legislation primarily offers subsidies for feedstock costs but does not cover operating or capital costs, making biofuels unattractive for producers amid concerns about tax rises and inflation (p. 256-257).

Market trends and demand analysis for solid biofuel

1.1.11 Overview of Solid Biofuels

Biofuels are fuels sourced directly or indirectly from biomass (Eurostat, 2023). They encompass liquid, solid, and gas fuels (Luque et al., 2008) and serve as renewable energy sources used for heating and cooling, electricity, and transportation (Stafford et al., 2019). This discussion focuses on solid biofuels.

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) (2022), "the African continent accounts for about 50% of the solid biofuels consumed worldwide. In sub-Saharan Africa alone, roughly 95% of the population depends on biomass in the form of fuelwood, charcoal, and residues" (IEA, 2022). In the Southern African region, traditional biomass energy products continue to dominate (Blignaut et al., 2011). With a significant portion of the population, particularly in rural areas, lacking access to electricity, affordable solid biomass energy sources like charcoal and firewood remain prevalent.

Solid biofuels offer several benefits compared to petroleum-based alternatives, including the reduction of air pollution and carbon emissions, while providing novel employment opportunities in rural contexts (Stafford et al., 2019).

Definition and types of solid biofuels

Primary Solid Biomass	
Traditional Uses (Mostly Residential)	Modern Uses (Mostly Industrial)
• Fuelwood (Firewood)	• Black liquor
• Charcoal	• Commercial Heat and Power Generation
• Dung	• Wood Pellet Heating Systems
• Crop Residues (Straw, Rice Husks)	

Source: Cushion et al., 2010, World Bank, p. 6

1.1.12 Firewood

Firewood refers to wood, typically in the form of trunks and branches of trees, that is normally burned for cooking, heating, or power generation (Sreevani, 2018). In South Africa, 96% of rural and 69% of low-income urban households rely on firewood to some degree (Shackleton et al., 2022, p. 1). Similarly, firewood remains a vital energy source in Botswana (Thakadu et al., 2020, p. 34) and is extensively used for cooking in Namibia (Nikodemus et al., 2023).

Households, particularly in rural areas, mostly gather firewood by themselves, free of charge. Its market accessibility and ease of entry make firewood widely accessible and a significant source of income for vulnerable urban and rural residents (Maes & Verbist, 2012, p. 4206). Firewood often helps women meet household expenses (Maes & Verbist, p. 4206). However, indoor cooking with firewood can release a high content of pollutant products of incomplete combustion (PIC), which can cause severe respiratory problems such as asthma (Maes & Verbist, p. 4207, Pallegedara & Kumara, 2022).

1.1.13 Charcoal

Approximately 90% of the annual wood harvest in Africa is used for energy consumption, with 20% of this volume processed into charcoal (FAO, 2017). Charcoal is a solid biomass fuel produced through the carbonisation of wood. It is widely used by low and middle-income families in African cities due to its affordability (Boniface, 2007). Charcoal can be purchased in small amounts, enabling households to make smaller payments, which adds to its affordability.

However, charcoal production is a major cause of natural woodland depletion in many African countries (Boniface, 2007, p. 67). Moreover, charcoal production and consumption are responsible for very high greenhouse gas emissions per unit of energy (Maes & Verbist, 2012, p. 4204). Additionally, charcoal can have serious health implications (Katherine et al., 2020). Thousands of deaths are attributed annually to overnight poisoning from carbon monoxide emitted by charcoal burning. In Africa specifically, 400,000 lives are taken

each year by indoor smoke from solid fuels (Maes & Verbist, 2012, p. 4208). While charcoal emissions are lower than those from firewood, during the cold start, charcoal stoves produce a large amount of smoke, which can negate the emission reduction (Maes & Verbist, 2012, p. 11).

1.1.14 Briquettes

Briquettes are compressed biomass molds that can complement charcoal or firewood if produced at a low cost and made accessible to consumers (Dinesha et al., 2019). Compared to conventional firewood, briquettes are cleaner, more conveniently sized, provide higher heat, and are easier to use (Dinesha et al., 2019).

Briquettes can be carbonised or non-carbonised. Carbonised briquettes are used for cooking or industrial purposes in Sub-Saharan households and businesses. They differ from charcoal in quality, emit less smoke but have higher ash content, and take longer to cook. Non-carbonised briquettes are cheaper but emit more smoke. Generally, briquettes require improved stoves, necessitating additional investments from users.

While cleaner than traditional biomass, briquettes have limitations. They take longer to warm up, are harder to ignite, and have a lower energy density than charcoal (Hosier et al., 2017).

1.1.15 Pellets

Pellets, produced from compressed dry biomass, are small cylinders typically 5–6 millimetres in diameter. While grilling with wood pellets has been shown to cause high levels of particulate matter emissions (Jelonek et al., 2021), their use with quality gasifier stoves offers high fuel efficiency. This results in reduced fuel consumption, easing pressure on natural resources and household budgets (Hosier et al., 2017).

1.1.16 Market Trends and Demand Analysis

In Sub-Saharan Africa, roughly 95% of the population relies on traditional solid fuels such as fuelwood, charcoal, and residues (IEA, 2022). Only about 11% use clean cooking fuels like LPG or electricity as their primary cooking fuel. Fewer than 1 million Sub-Saharan households (less than 0.5% of the region's population) use alternative biomass fuels such as pellets, carbonised, and non-carbonised briquettes (World Bank, 2017).

Affordability is a key barrier to the widespread adoption of alternative biomass fuels in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly for the approximately 50% of households that rely on free firewood collection for cooking. Many cannot afford, or are unwilling to pay for, cleaner fuels and the accompanying improved cookstoves. This challenge is especially acute for rural and many urban consumers. Despite this, there is a burgeoning market for alternative biomass fuels (World Bank, 2017).

Botswana

Household consumers in Botswana mostly purchase charcoal and firewood directly from small-scale retailers, including supermarkets, gas stations, kiosks, open-air stalls, and wholesalers' shops or warehouses. Transactions are typically made via card payments and cash up front. Small-scale retailers are mainly located at shopping centres or along roads, with only a small fraction in the local market. While most wholesalers deliver products in bulk on the same day, most retail sellers often do not offer delivery services to customers,

and if they do, it may take longer than a week. Customers thus most frequently buy energy sources directly from shops, kiosks, stalls, etc. (SBA D9.3, 2023).

Namibia

In Namibia, charcoal is predominantly used by affluent households for leisure activities such as barbecues. Firewood is popular among lower-income and rural households, with most households preferring to collect firewood on their own instead of opting for commercialised firewood. Urban and peri-urban households use firewood mainly for cooking traditional meals. Marketers and suppliers of cooking and heating energy sources in Namibia are mostly wholesalers and small-scale businesses (including kiosks, retailers, and open-air stalls) primarily located in urban areas. Most customers are households and local businesses who purchase fuel sources directly from the shop. Small-scale businesses often place orders by phone to resupply their inventory from one to three different suppliers of firewood and charcoal located within the same city or town (SBA D9.3, 2023).

South Africa

In South Africa's urban areas, electricity and LPG are the most common energy sources. In peri-urban areas, electricity, firewood, or gas prevail, while rural areas favour electricity, firewood, and paraffin or LPG. Similar to Botswana and Namibia, charcoal is used mainly for barbecues and other social activities. Small-scale retailers, kiosks, and open-air stalls in South Africa are predominantly based in peri-urban areas, with the remainder located on the roadside or at shop owners' houses in rural areas. Most small businesses do not offer delivery services, so their main customers, including households and local businesses, need to pick up their orders routinely. Small-scale businesses predominantly order products via phone calls and supplier distribution centres in the same area (SBA D9.3, 2023).

Steambioafrica (SBA) solid biofuel

According to Biggs (2009, p. 86), "of the biomass energy supply in Africa, some 90% is used in households with extremely wasteful traditional cookstoves that typically attain barely 5-15% efficiency." Inefficiency in biomass fuel conversion is responsible for considerable indoor air pollution and respiratory diseases, while emitting high amounts of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The SteamBioAfrica **(SBA) solid biofuel sought to address these shortcomings.**

Produced using superheated steam (SHS) technology through a torrefaction process, the SBA solid biofuel transforms wood chips from encroaching and invasive bush species sourced locally in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa into a clean-burning solid biofuel and water.

1.1.17 Product Strengths

The characteristics of the SBA solid biofuel offer several advantages that can outperform competing products on the market, particularly traditional biomass sources like charcoal, firewood, wood pellets, and wood chips. During the sales trials, many of these superior qualities were confirmed, with some areas for potential product optimisation identified.

Advantages of the SBA Solid Biofuel

- **Reduced smoke:** Generates less smoke, reducing health-related hazards compared to conventional biofuels such as firewood and charcoal.
- **SHS technology:** Produced using superheated steam (SHS) technology, enabling the consistent and ongoing conversion of high-volume bush into fuel. This process produces minimal environmental emissions, helping to combat climate change, and aligns with international sustainable development objectives.
- **Hydrophobic nature:** The biofuel is very dry and does not easily get mouldy, allowing for easy and longer storage. Its dryness also makes it easily ignitable, offering convenience and ease of use, which may enhance consumer acceptance.
- **Local and natural raw materials:** Made from 100% local and natural raw materials, supporting local economies and reducing the carbon footprint from transportation.

The SBA solid biofuel can provide households with an **affordable, environmentally friendly alternative** to current product offerings available on the market. By prioritising affordability, sustainability, and user-friendliness, the biofuel addresses the diverse needs of consumers while promoting environmental stewardship.

Furthermore, widespread commercialisation and availability of the SBA solid biofuel can contribute to enhancing local livelihoods. The SHS technology itself **promotes food security** by alleviating land degradation due to widespread bush encroachment and **creates new jobs and income streams** through the deployment and operation of the SHS plant in rural areas, where unemployment levels are high. By stimulating the harvesting of encroaching and invasive bush species, the technology **can facilitate sustainable ecosystem management and land restoration**. Hence, the deployment of the SHS technology along with the solid biofuel could contribute to generating sustainable, clean, and affordable energy in Africa, thereby accelerating the implementation of commitments under the Paris Agreement and the EU Green Deal.

1.1.18 Competition and Demand

As a new product, the SBA solid biofuel is expected to face competition from existing solid biofuels such as charcoal, firewood, briquettes, and wood pellets (Section 3.1). These products have a more established market, and consumers are more familiar with them. Nevertheless, leveraging the unique characteristics and benefits of the SBA solid biofuel—such as affordability, convenience, ease of use, and its environmental and health benefits—could position it favourably in the market.

1.1.19 Distribution

The SBA project leveraged the existing value chains of charcoal and firewood to introduce the SBA solid biofuel to local markets. By utilising established distribution networks, including retailers, local vendors, kiosks, and transportation networks that already meet the demand for conventional biomass fuels, the project aimed to effectively reach target consumers and promote the adoption of the SBA solid biofuel.

During this trial phase, the project collaborated with selected small sellers in Windhoek and Gaborone to sell the solid biofuel to their existing customers (households) and gather consumer feedback. Direct engagement with households was crucial, as the goal of Work Package 10 (WP10) was to promote widespread commercialisation of the new solid biofuel in the downstream biomass value chains, with a focus on consumer acceptance. WP10 complemented Work Package 12 (WP12), which targeted industrial consumers (cement

factories, breweries, foundries, etc.) in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa for market prioritisation and project result exploitation.

1.1.20 Pricing

The project undertook a benchmarking exercise, comparing the prices of charcoal, firewood, and LPG, to define an acceptable price range for the SBA solid biofuel (see Figure 4). The benchmarked prices were used during the SBA solid biofuel sales trials, providing a practical and effective method for gauging competitiveness, communicating value to consumers, and ensuring the affordability of the solid biofuel.

By benchmarking the price of the solid biofuel against charcoal and firewood—conventional biomass fuels widely used in the three countries, especially in areas with limited access to modern energy sources like electricity and LPG—the SBA project aimed to effectively communicate the cost-effectiveness of the new biofuel. Priced competitively within EUR 0.175 - 0.58 per kg against charcoal and firewood, the goal was to make the solid biofuel a more attractive option for consumers, potentially driving uptake.

LPG serves as an additional benchmark for comparison because it is widely used for cooking, particularly in South Africa. However, following the COVID-19 pandemic, LPG prices skyrocketed, rendering it unaffordable to poorer households.

Figure 4: National Average retail prices for charcoal and firewood in Botswana (Source: Authors, 2024)

Sustainable business models: analysis and validation

A business model is core to any business, defined as "a model representation of the logical relationships between how an organisation or company can generate added value for customers and secure a profit for the organisation" (Gabler, online). A viable business model helps a business stay competitive by identifying the unique value it offers to customers.

In the context of sustainability, the concept of a business model is taken to the next level. Lüdeke-Freund et al. (2018) define it as "about creating significantly increased positive effects and/or significantly reduced negative effects on the natural environment and society through changes in the way a company and its network create, deliver, and capture value." This concept has been promoted to enhance the co-creation of business and sustainability benefits (Baldassarre et al., 2020).

Sustainability can be understood in many different ways. This SteamBioAfrica project report seeks to link the business model concept with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Figure 5 illustrates how a business model (BM) can contribute to the SDGs in the long run (Mutta et al., 2021).

Figure 5: Contribution of business models to SDGs

Source: Authors, adapted from UN.ORG

A sustainable business model comprises several key components. This report focuses on the following elements: value proposition, customer relationship, value creation and delivery, and economic value capture.

Value Proposition

A key value proposition is a simple statement that summarises why a customer would choose a product or service. It encompasses the product and the associated services offered to customer segments. Four aspects are found to be key to the SBA solid biofuel: product quality, price, packaging and service:

- **Quality:** The solid biofuel is light, dry, and hydrophobic, making it easy to handle and store for a longer shelf life. It lights quickly and generates less smoke compared to traditional solid biofuels

such as firewood and charcoal, offering health benefits to users. The SBA solid biofuel is produced in an eco-friendly manner from problematic encroacher bush.

- **Pricing:** Ensuring competitive pricing that makes the solid biofuel an attractive alternative to traditional energy sources (firewood, charcoal) without compromising affordability.
- **Product packaging:** The use of sustainable packaging that not only preserves product quality but also appeals to consumer preferences and promotes ease of use. Given its dry and hydrophobic nature, there are several packaging options to consider for the solid biofuel beyond the plastic bags used during the sales trials. One approach is a packageless option, where customers bring their own packaging. Alternatively, as the product becomes more established in the market, alternative packaging such as paper bags could also be explored.
- **Service-quality dimensions:** Making the solid biofuel available at conveniently located sales points to facilitate purchase for consumers. It also entails building and maintaining good customer relationships based on reliability and trustworthiness, fostering customer loyalty and positive word-of-mouth (Mutta et al., 2021).

Customer Segments

Customer segments refer to "the people a business intends to market a product or service to" (Sibaliya et al., 2021, p. 2). In businesses, customers are often segmented into distinct, internally homogenous groups based on characteristics such as demographics, behaviour, and preferences. This allows the specific needs and wants of different groups to be explored, enabling product and service offerings to be tailored to better suit their needs (Cooil et al., 2008, p. 10).

The main customer segments for solid biofuel in both Botswana and Namibia include:

- B2B Customers: Small retailers, kiosks, and shops.
- B2C Customers: Households, roadside food vendors, and institutions.

Strategically segmenting these groups will enable targeted and personalised marketing approaches, fostering increased adoption and widespread distribution of solid biofuel while ensuring customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Customer Relationship

Building strong customer relationships is essential for maximising customer satisfaction, loyalty, and lifetime value, driving sustainable business growth. This involves:

- Nurturing relationships through personalised experiences.
- Implementing strategic customer engagement and effective data management.
- Providing personalised customer service and loyalty programs for both B2B and B2C segments.
- Establishing feedback mechanisms to assess solid biofuel quality and service satisfaction.
- Continuously improving operations and building trust in biofuel supply.
- Offering comprehensive product information and educational resources to enhance customer relationships, satisfaction, and loyalty in the solid biofuel market.

Value Creation and Delivery

Value creation and delivery are crucial aspects of a successful business strategy, involving:

- A comprehensive approach to understanding customer needs.
- Developing innovative products and effectively bringing these offerings to the market.
- Conducting market research, gathering customer feedback, and using data analytics to identify opportunities for improvement.
- Fostering a culture of innovation and ensuring high-quality standards.
- Managing efficient supply chains through strong supplier relationships.
- Strategic collaborations with other value chain actors and targeted marketing strategies to meet customer requirements and generate revenue.

Economic Value Capture

Maximising economic value within a business involves a strategic balance between revenue generation and cost management. To achieve this, businesses focus on:

- Efficiently identifying and capitalising on revenue streams through product innovation, effective marketing, and diversification efforts.
- Employing rigorous cost management strategies such as resource optimisation, process streamlining, and favorable supplier negotiations to contain operational expenses.
- Implementing pricing strategies that consider factors like perceived value, cost-plus models, and dynamic market conditions.

1.1.21 Identified Business Models for MSMEs

Figure 6 presents a tool used by the project to identify biomass downstream value chain actors and their possible business models relevant to the commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel. The tool differentiates enterprises based on their formal/informal status and business size.

In the initial phase of biofuel commercialisation, the SBA project introduced the solid biofuel to local markets in Botswana and Namibia through small actors such as kiosks and gas stations. Due to the size of their businesses, big retailers, wholesalers, and distributors were initially unwilling to stock the SBA solid biofuel. As a new product, it was considered 'risky' because customers were not yet familiar with it. Understanding the business models of each group of value chain actors helped the project employ different strategies in communicating the product and its marketing with each actor.

Figure 6: Solid biofuel commercialisation strategies (Source: Authors, 2024)

Formal vs Informal Enterprises

- **Formal Enterprises:** Adhere to regulatory frameworks, engage in structured supply chains, and often leverage institutional support. Their business models typically prioritise scalability, efficiency, and adherence to national, regional, and international standards, facilitating access to funding, technology, and global markets.
- **Informal Businesses:** Lack formal structures and resources but operate within local communities, harnessing indigenous knowledge, informal networks, and flexible strategies to navigate challenges and seize opportunities in the biomass sector. They often cater to underserved communities and neighbourhoods, contributing to livelihoods and socio-economic resilience at the grassroots level.

Wholesalers and Big Retailers (Supermarkets)

- Have substantial influence in the biomass-based market due to their financial capacity and physical presence.
- Can buy in bulk from fuel producers and sell to consumers, with an interest in maintaining their market position.
- May not be initially attracted to the SBA solid biofuel, a new product, due to the lack of established demand.

Small Sellers (Kiosks and Open-Air Sellers)

- More open to trying and selling new products.
- Have limited market share but significant physical presence, influencing household consumers through personal relationships with regular customers.

- Easier to approach and communicate with, as the SBA project team had personal connections with these sellers. In Namibia, N-Big, a project partner, managed to engage several small sellers to test selling the solid biofuel.

Informal Online Sellers

- Have a wider outreach and offer the convenience of online transactions.
- Often lack physical shops and have limited interest in trying out new products like the SBA solid biofuel.

Gas Stations (Botswana):

BITRI, a project partner in Botswana, approached several gas stations to test selling the solid biofuel. Introducing and selling the new solid biofuel at gas stations was straightforward because these retailers already offered a variety of fuels, such as firewood and charcoal.

- Gas stations primarily depend on consumers visiting the premises, limiting their influence over encouraging customers to experiment with new products like the SBA solid biofuel.

1.1.22 Viable Business Models

The identification of viable business models (BMs) suitable for the new solid biofuel is key to product commercialisation efforts. Using the tool in Figure 6 and a sustainable business model canvas, this report identified several business models suitable for short-, medium-, and long-term (post-project) commercialisation. These models are initially categorised into two groups described below:

1.1.23 Business model category #1: Retailers and gas stations – formal

Figure 7 presents a business model category involving formal retailers, which includes physical stores and gas stations. In the three countries, gas stations sell various kinds of fuels, including firewood and charcoal.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 7: SBA solid biofuel BMC for retailers and gas stations (Source: Authors, 2024)

Value Proposition

As described in Figure 7, the key value proposition when retailers market the SBA solid biofuel to customers lies in the product's characteristics and quality. Key attributes of the SBA solid biofuel, including potential health benefits due to reduced smoke emissions, convenient storage, and an extended shelf life compared to traditional biofuels, contribute to its wider consumer acceptance. Additionally, since the biofuel is new to the local markets, pricing is also a crucial consideration. It should be affordable and competitive with other fuels such as firewood, charcoal, pellets, or briquettes.

Customer segment

Retailers' primary market consists of barbecue grillers ("kapana" / "braai"), food vendors, and households who purchase based on their needs. Additionally, stalls, kiosks, and roadside sellers who resell the solid biofuel at a higher price are part of this market.

Customer relationships

Customers frequently visit retail stores and gas stations, putting these establishments in a better position to collect feedback and gain customer insights for product improvement. Service-quality dimensions include easy access to retail stores or gas stations, with clear and longer opening hours compared to informal roadside sellers. Product availability, quality, and price are generally consistent at these retailers, offering reliability and trustworthiness to customers.

Good customer relations are important for business success. Therefore, retailers can consider offering additional services, such as "order by phone" or "same day" home delivery, to customers living within a certain distance.

Value creation and delivery

In this business model, value creation and delivery involve several key activities, such as purchasing, transporting, marketing, and information processing, particularly for large retailers. Most of the retailer's time is dedicated to selling and marketing. To create product awareness and encourage customer uptake of the solid biofuel, retailers could offer in-store product demonstrations.

Essential resources include the SBA solid biofuel, personnel, vehicles (pickups, trucks) for product transport, storage facilities, and utilities such as electricity, water, and telecommunication. These resources, along with other necessary infrastructure, are vital for smooth business operations. Achieving efficiency in resource utilisation can contribute to retailers' increased revenue and profitability.

Retailers rely on key partners such as suppliers, wholesalers, distributors, and transporters to ensure seamless operations. These partnerships are crucial for maintaining a steady supply chain and efficient distribution network. Moreover, retailers can leverage their key partnerships, built on relationships and trust over the years, to achieve cost reduction through price discounts or "pay later" services.

Retailers utilise various channels based on their size, including physical stores like supermarkets, direct marketing strategies, dedicated sales departments, customer hotlines, and delivery services. These diverse channels enable retailers to effectively reach and serve their customers, ensuring the SBA solid biofuel is accessible to customers at any time.

Economic value capture

The cost structure encompasses all expenses associated with procuring, transporting, and selling the solid biofuel, as well as other products, covering both fixed and variable costs. This includes acquisition costs, transportation expenses, storage fees, marketing expenditures, and overhead costs essential for maintaining operations and facilitating sales. Driving operational costs down can contribute to retailers' increased revenue and profitability.

Revenue streams are mainly driven by direct sales to customers who purchase goods with immediate payment ("cash and carry"). Retailers can consider extending a credit facility to established B2B clients, such as small retailers, schools, and public offices. This fosters long-term relationships and ensures a steady income over time. Revenue is generated through transaction-based means, including cash and carry transactions and providing credits to long-term or trusted business clients.

SWOT Analysis of the Identified Business Models

Strengths

Retailers, both large and small, have a diverse customer base, including households, restaurants, and businesses, providing a broad market for the SBA solid biofuel. Retail stores, as the final sale point, are geographically widespread and enjoy a strong local presence, particularly in urban and peri-urban areas of the three countries. The key value proposition for retailers is the convenience they offer customers, including easily accessible locations. This geographical reach is important for the commercialisation of SBA solid biofuel by lowering operational, delivery, and storage costs. Large retailers can purchase solid biofuel in bulk and sell

it in smaller units, leveraging economies of scale to offer affordable prices and ensure consistent availability. They also have the capacity and space to store large quantities of biofuel. Additionally, some retailers can provide repackaging, branding, and marketing services for the solid biofuel.

Weaknesses

Retailers may initially hesitate to stock the solid biofuel due to unclear supply and demand dynamics. This hesitation was confirmed during sales trials, where major retailers were reluctant to trial SBA solid biofuel. Uncertainty about consumer interest and a lack of knowledge about the product's specific qualities and benefits can make retailers cautious. Without a clear understanding of its advantages and market potential, they may be unwilling to allocate shelf space or invest in initial stock.

The novelty of the SBA solid biofuel in the market requires significant promotion and education efforts. Retailers might be hesitant to invest in marketing and educating customers, especially if they are already managing a diverse range of items. This hesitation can slow down the adoption and penetration of the solid biofuel in the local markets. Retailers may also face logistical challenges with storage and handling.

While large retailers often have the capacity for bulk storage, smaller retailers might struggle with space constraints, affecting product availability. The need for flexible financing options for consumers could pose a risk for retailers. Offering instalment plans or deferred payments might impact their cash flow and financial stability, particularly if consumers default on payments. This financial risk lowers the possibility of offering financing options to customers to quickly promote the solid biofuel, thereby slowing down product penetration.

Opportunities

Retailers can play a crucial role in ensuring that SBA solid biofuel reaches consumers due to the product variety and convenience they offer. An initial stock of SBA solid biofuel could be supplied at a discounted price, encouraging retailers to restock if their experience is positive, thus creating a niche market. Large retailers can provide financing options such as monthly instalments or deferred payments, encouraging consumers to purchase the new biofuel.

Retailers often have in-house branded products like firewood and charcoal, benefiting from customer loyalty. SBA solid biofuel can leverage this brand loyalty to gain market traction, where retailers can sell the solid biofuel using their in-house brands. Retailers, with their established market relationships and marketing channels, are well-positioned to promote and market the new SBA solid biofuel. Furthermore, offering SBA solid biofuel alongside complementary products like improved cookstoves can enhance its appeal. Flexible packaging options can also take advantage of the product's ease of storage, providing additional convenience to consumers.

Challenges

The SBA solid biofuel has strong competition risks from competing alternative products such as charcoal, firewood, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). Fuel choice typically depends on availability, consumer preference, price, convenience, and, at times, social status associated with using certain types of fuels like LPG. Ideally, SBA solid biofuel should be targeted to the customer segment that uses firewood and charcoal because the biofuel can be more competitive, convenient, and efficient for this segment.

1.1.24 Business model category #2: kiosks, roadside vendors, open-air stalls and shops – informal

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 8: SBA solid biofuel BMC for informal kiosks, shops, roadside vendors, and open-air stalls (Source: Authors, 2024)

Value Proposition

The key value proposition in this business model depends on the product, SBA solid biofuel, and the convenience offered by informal kiosks, shops, roadside vendors, and open-air stalls. These outlets are strategically located in customer neighbourhoods, ensuring easy access.

The performance of this business model depends on the characteristics and quality of the solid biofuel and how it is perceived by customers. Additionally, its price competitiveness compared to other solid biofuels sold by these vendors, such as firewood or charcoal, plays a key role. Attributes like the potential health benefits due to reduced smoke emissions, convenience in storage, and extended shelf life compared to traditional biofuels would also contribute to its wider consumer acceptance.

Customer Segments and Relations

The primary customer segments in this business model include households and micro-businesses, such as street food vendors, operating in rural, urban, and peri-urban centres. These customers seek a cost-effective and convenient fuel source for everyday cooking needs. Customers primarily purchase the solid biofuel directly from informal small sellers, who market the product in smaller quantities to cater to diverse customers with varying budgets. This approach relies on customer referrals to expand its customer base through positive word-of-mouth recommendations.

Value Creation and Delivery

The key activities of informal small-scale sellers include purchasing SBA solid biofuel from large-scale retailers or wholesalers and selling it at a slightly higher price. These sellers buy the solid biofuel from larger retailers and local suppliers, then sell directly to household customers and micro-businesses. Marketing efforts are crucial, with sellers promoting their business through word of mouth, roadside signage, and social media platforms like WhatsApp to attract and retain customers.

Key partners include large-scale retailers and wholesalers providing SBA solid biofuel. Partnerships are established with supermarkets and larger retailers for bulk purchasing, as well as with local suppliers. Informal small sellers can leverage on key partnerships by ensuring on-time payments. As the partnerships and trust grow, small sellers could ask for discounts or deferred payments.

Key resources include a kiosk or table set up at a strategic roadside location, a motorcycle for transporting biofuels, and a smartphone for managing orders and communication, ensuring efficient and streamlined operations.

Channels for reaching customers include direct sales from the roadside kiosk or at local fresh markets, leveraging word-of-mouth referrals to expand the customer base, and taking orders via phone or WhatsApp for added convenience.

Economic Value Capture

Cost structure components include procurement costs, which are expenses related to buying the solid biofuel from suppliers, transportation costs for delivering the solid biofuel to the selling point, operational costs associated with running the kiosk, including maintenance and minor repairs, and marketing costs for small promotional activities and materials.

Revenue could come from: a) direct sales through cash transactions at a roadside kiosk, catering to individual customers, b) bulk orders from other small businesses purchasing biofuels in larger quantities, and c) product bundling of the solid biofuel with other products.

SWOT Analysis of the Identified Business Models

Strengths

This business model capitalises on strategic strengths to establish a competitive edge for SBA solid biofuel in local markets. Firstly, the biofuel offers distinct advantages over traditional choices like firewood and charcoal, including reduced smoke emissions ("good for the climate"), easy handling and storage, long shelf life, and sustainability. Secondly, the business model employs a wide distribution network involving informal kiosks and roadside vendors, which are dominant players in local markets due to their numbers and geographic coverage. These vendors are not only present in urban and peri-urban areas but are also widely spread in rural areas. This setup enhances accessibility for households and micro-businesses and ensures adaptability in responding to local market dynamics and preferences.

Additionally, strong customer relationships fostered through word-of-mouth referrals are pivotal in driving market uptake of the solid biofuel. Finally, the cost-effective operational approach, relying on micro- and small-scale sellers, minimises overhead costs and enhances operational flexibility to meet fluctuating market demands.

Weaknesses

Reliance on informal small-scale sellers may pose significant challenges in ensuring consistent supply, quality control and maintaining high service standards, which can ultimately jeopardise the reputation of the SBA solid biofuel. Additionally, dependence on large retailers and suppliers for sourcing the solid biofuel introduces risks such as supply chain disruptions, logistical issues, and fluctuating procurement costs. These factors can further complicate the stability and predictability of operations.

Opportunities

The flexibility of sales locations offers the opportunity to reach a broader customer base. For instance, roadside vendors can sell to passersby who might not otherwise engage with the product. The informal nature of these sales outlets allows sellers to adapt more easily to local preferences, offering the product in loose packaging to meet varying demand quantities for local customers. Additionally, this business model benefits from lower administrative costs and reduced expenses for rent or personnel, making it more economical to operate. This can potentially increase profitability and, consequently, the popularity of the business among sellers.

Threats / Challenges

The SBA solid biofuel is targeted at households in developing countries that rely on firewood or charcoal for daily cooking. In urban and peri-urban areas, this customer segment presents low market risks due to the scarcity of firewood in cities. However, in rural areas, the market risks are higher due to the abundant availability of firewood, as people can harvest it from forests on community lands.

To mitigate these risks, sellers should target a diverse customer base. It is preferable for the business to serve both households and institutional customers. Additionally, sellers could enter into bulk contractual arrangements with institutional customers to secure assured sales.

1.1.25 Verified businesses and viable business models

From the above two categories, the following **four business models** are proposed for the commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel: cash and carry, product bundling, distributor business models and e-commerce.

1.1.26 Viable business model #1: Cash and carry

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 9: Generic Business Model Canvas for Cash and Carry (Source: Authors, 2024)

The **cash-and-carry business model** for SBA solid biofuel involves customers paying in full at the time of purchase and taking the product with them immediately. This model is both viable and adaptable, fitting well within both formal and informal settings for sellers.

Key Features of the Cash and Carry Model

- **Direct sales:** Customers purchase the solid biofuel in small quantities or in bulk directly from the retail or gas station. This eliminates the need for middlemen, reduces costs and allows for competitive pricing of the SBA solid biofuel.
- **Upfront payment:** All transactions are conducted on a cash basis, meaning customers pay at the point of sale. This ensures immediate revenue and reduces credit risk for the business.
- **Bulk pricing:** This model also allows the retailer or gas station to offer the solid biofuel in large quantities, encouraging bulk purchases particularly from small retailers, vendors or kiosks. This can lower the price per unit for the customer and increase sales volume for the business.
- **Location and accessibility:** The business typically operates from a strategic location that is easily accessible to target customers that use the solid biofuel for cooking or heating.

Benefits and Challenges of the Cash and Carry Business Model

Benefits	Challenges
<p>Lower prices: By avoiding the additional costs of delivery and credit sales, customers can benefit from lower prices, making the solid biofuel more attractive.</p> <p>Immediate revenue: The upfront payment model ensures that the business has immediate access to cash flow, which can be reinvested into operations or growth.</p> <p>Reduced credit risk: Eliminating credit sales reduces the risk of non-payment, enhancing the financial stability of the business.</p>	<p>Customer inconvenience: Potential customers will need a mode of transportation to facilitate the transaction, especially when ordering large quantities.</p> <p>Limited reach: This model primarily targets local or regional customers with cash on hand, which may limit market reach compared to delivery-based services or those offering financing options.</p>

1.1.27 Viable business model #2: SBA solid biofuel product bundling

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 10: Generic Business Model Canvas for Solid Biofuel Product Bundling (Source: Authors, 2024)

The **product bundling business** model involves selling multiple products together with the SBA solid biofuel as a single combined package in order to enhance value for customers, increase sales, and improve efficiency for businesses. Product bundling is a viable business model that falls within the two categories mentioned above. However, it would work best for both Business model #1 and Business model #2.

The SBA solid biofuel might not work with any existing stove and cooking tools, and thus **bundling it with improved cook stoves** is fundamental for creating usability among consumers. Furthermore, as SBA solid biofuel works great as a fire starter, bundling with the traditional fuel sources in local shops to enhance the overall experience in cooking or heating would also help to foster product adoption for customers to get used to and repurchase the product on a frequent basis. Retailers could offer this opportunity as they usually already stock and sell many other established and competing fuel sources. Building such relationships with customers paves the way to long-term, affordable last mile distribution of SBA solid biofuel products.

Key Features of the SBA Product Bundling Model

- SBA product bundle consisting of the solid biofuel and one or more other products that complement it, sold together at a combined price. The solid biofuel can be bundled with energy efficient cook stoves or with firewood or charcoal for those who would like to **use it as a fire lighter**.
- SBA product bundle offered at a (discounted) price that is lower than the sum of individual items if bought separately to incentivize and attract customers.

Benefits and Challenges of the SBA Product Bundling Model	
Benefits	Challenges
<p>Increased sales volume: Customers are more likely to purchase greater quantities of the SBA solid biofuel when it is bundled with other products and offered at a discount.</p> <p>Reaching a broader customer base: Bundling provides an opportunity to attract early adopters during the initial launch period of the SBA solid biofuel by offering a more competitive and user-friendly product mix.</p> <p>Enhanced customer experience: It streamlines the purchasing process for customers looking to buy complementary items, such as cookstoves or multiple different fuel sources, at once.</p> <p>Customer perception: Customers perceive savings due to feeling they are getting more value for their money.</p> <p>Differentiation: Unique bundles can help the SBA solid biofuel and its sellers differentiate themselves in the competitive market.</p>	<p>Loss in revenue: Discounts in bundling can reduce profit margins if not managed correctly.</p> <p>Customer perception: Brand image of the SBA solid biofuel can be jeopardised if it is frequently sold at a discount in bundles together with other products.</p> <p>Mispricing and inventory management: Bundling requires a thorough understanding of the market and careful planning to ensure efficient pricing and sufficient stock levels of each product included in the bundle.</p>

1.1.28 Viable business model #3: SBA solid biofuel distributor

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

Figure 11: Generic Business Model Canvas for Solid Biofuel Distributor (Source: Authors)

The solid biofuel **distributor business model** involves a business purchasing the SBA solid biofuel directly from the SHS plant (currently located at the Cheetah Conservation Fund in Otjiwarongo, Namibia) and reselling it to other businesses including retailers, wholesalers, and other smaller businesses who in turn sell it to the end consumer. Acting as an intermediary, the distributor bridges the gap between production and the end market, ensuring that solid biofuel is available to consumers through various retail channels. Distributor is a viable business model that falls within only the first category of formal sellers.

Key Features of the SBA Solid Biofuel Distributor

Distributors typically handle large quantities of products, benefiting from economies of scale and logistical efficiencies. They play a crucial role in the supply chain by facilitating the flow of goods from manufacturers to the market, providing storage and inventory management, and offering additional services such as marketing support and customer service. The SBA Solid Biofuel Distributor will supply solid biofuel to wholesalers, retailers, and smaller businesses in substantial quantities through reliable, timely delivery services, and at competitive prices. In addition, the distributor will

- Collaborate with transportation partners e.g. logistics companies or develop in-house transportation capabilities to facilitate efficient delivery of SBA solid biofuel to customers.
- Conduct strategic marketing initiatives to promote SBA solid biofuel brand awareness and product adoption.
- Maintain adequate inventory levels to meet customer demand while minimising excess stock.

- Organise efficient distribution channels to deliver SBA solid biofuel to various customer segments.

Benefits and Challenges of the SBA Solid Biofuel Distributor	
Benefits	Challenges
<p>Wide scope of customers: The business model targets a diverse customer base, including retailers, wholesalers, restaurants, and food businesses. This diversity helps to stabilise revenue streams and reduces dependency on any single market segment.</p> <p>Market expertise: Extensive knowledge of the market, including customer preferences, competitive landscape, and regulatory requirements, can help in strategically positioning SBA solid biofuel.</p> <p>Established networks: Distributors have existing relationships with retailers, wholesalers, and end-users, facilitating quicker and broader market penetration of the solid biofuel.</p> <p>Broader product outreach: Working with suppliers and transportation partners reinforces the supply chain, guaranteeing extensive and efficient solid biofuel distribution.</p>	<p>Complexity in logistics management: Managing transportation logistics for distributing the solid biofuel to various customer segments can be complex and costly, particularly during peak demand periods or in remote areas.</p> <p>Keeping price advantage: The involvement of a central distributor and each seller in the sales process requires additional mark-ups and overhead costs, increasing the final price paid by customers compared to direct sales.</p> <p>Customer relationship management: Building and maintaining direct relationships with end customers can be more challenging when a distributor acts as the intermediary, potentially impacting customer loyalty and feedback loops.</p>

1.1.29 Viable business model #4: SBA solid biofuel e-commerce

Sustainable Business Model Canvas

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401

Figure 12: Generic Business Model Canvas for SBA Solid Biofuel E-Commerce (Source: Authors)

When adopting the **Solid Biofuel E-Commerce business model**, businesses in Botswana, Namibia, or South Africa could set up their own online store or opt for platforms that are already available and operate in their locations. Existing platforms could include international platforms such as Ubuy: <https://www.ubuy.co.com/> and Amazon: <https://www.amazon.com/> which are available in South Africa and Botswana but have high delivery fees; or regional and country-specific platforms such as SkyMart: <https://www.skymartbw.com/> (Botswana) and SmartGuds: <https://www.smartguds.com/> (Namibia). E-Commerce is a viable business model that only applies for Business model #1 option.

Key Features of the SBA Solid Biofuel E-Commerce

- Setting up an online store for the solid biofuel will require investing in e-commerce platform development, secure payment gateways, and optimising the user experience. On the other hand, leveraging established e-commerce platforms offers immediate access to a large customer base but involves understanding the platform's rules, algorithms, and competition.
- Order fulfilment: managing inventory, packing, and shipping orders.
- Implementing a subscription model will require careful consideration of pricing and the overall customer experience. For this option, businesses will have to offer unique value propositions that encourage customers to subscribe and continue their subscriptions for the solid biofuel over time.

Benefits and Challenges of the SBA Solid Biofuel E-Commerce Business Model

Benefits	Challenges
<p>Ease of purchase and delivery: Provides an easy and convenient way for consumers to purchase the solid biofuel online, with doorstep delivery options.</p> <p>Customer education and perception: Offers educational resources and intuitive information on product placement and advantages, helping consumers make informed decisions and use the solid biofuel effectively.</p> <p>Reach of customers: Offers the business access to a growing market of environmentally conscious consumers who prefer sustainable energy solutions.</p> <p>Customer stickiness: Offers the business an opportunity to build a loyal customer base through subscription models and superior customer service.</p> <p>Transparent sales data: Enables the business to scale operations efficiently by leveraging data analytics and optimising supply chain management.</p>	<p>Upfront cost requirement: Significant initial investment required for developing a custom e-commerce platform, integrating secure payment gateways, and optimising the user experience.</p> <p>Inventory management: Significant costs associated with inventory management, warehousing, and logistics partnerships.</p> <p>Overhead costs associated with platforms: Potential difficulties in navigating the competitive landscape on established e-commerce platforms, including understanding platform algorithms, rules, and dealing with platform fees.</p> <p>Supply chain management: Managing the complexities of supply chain logistics, including inventory management, packing, and shipping, to ensure timely and efficient order fulfilment may prove challenging.</p>

Financing and investment options

Funding and Investment Requirements

Increased **investments in modern bioenergy present a promising strategy** for enhancing Africa's energy access and security, reducing global carbon dioxide emissions, and enabling African countries to attract investment and technology. This, in turn, would allow African countries to achieve greater energy self-sufficiency, stimulate income and employment generation, and become significant global exporters of food and biofuels. More broadly, these developments could drastically lower poverty indices, supporting "food and energy security, sustainable management, and use of natural resources" (Hofmann & Khatun, 2013, p. 374).

This **Deliverable 10.4 report** provides a brief overview of the main financial interventions required for the commercial success of the verified business models, in relation to the SteamBioAfrica Deliverable D10.5 report on the innovative financing toolbox for biomass MSMEs (CSCP, 2024). The report focuses on funding and investment barriers and opportunities for the commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel and offers valuable insights on the way forward.

Firstly, MSMEs are especially vital players for the commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel among the downstream actors of the biomass value chain. MSMEs constitute the largest portion of most economies globally (SBA D10.5, 2024) and are considered by many to have a potential impact on achieving many of the sustainable development goals far greater than their size (Endris & Kassegn, 2022, p. 1). Endris and Kassegn (2022, p. 13) reviewed MSMEs' potential role in the sustainable development of Sub-Saharan Africa, identifying that "lack of access to finance, poor infrastructure, and entrepreneurial attitudes are main challenges facing MSMEs in sub-Saharan Africa." These challenges were exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which put several MSMEs at risk of permanent closure (p. 13).

As mentioned earlier, the SteamBioAfrica's Deliverable 9.3 report, tasked with identifying viable business models for the market development of the SBA solid biofuel, outlined the current status of **green financing and investment** in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa, highlighting opportunities for their stimulation (BITRI, 2023).

The report found that while the green finance landscape in Botswana is not yet fully developed, the national government is committed to strengthening it. Funds for green projects, natural resource management, and climate change mitigation initiatives are increasingly being awarded, and community-led projects and citizen business ventures are receiving more government support (SBA D9.3, 2023).

Similarly, Namibia has established several financing institutions for the biomass sector through commercial banks and development finance entities, offering loans and grants. In South Africa, climate finance is supported by a broad network of organisations, with funding primarily occurring through banks. Additionally, there are special funds dedicated to the green economy and catalysing the early-stage development of businesses (SBA D9.3, BITRI, 2023).

Robust and sustainable financing mechanisms are required to ensure the widespread dissemination of improved biomass technologies, such as the SHS technology. The private sector—including individuals, producers' unions, and associations developing fuel—can be stimulated to promote these technologies through targeted policy and legal tools. Those working on developing improved technologies can be supported through the provision of "credit facilities, training, production space, and production equipment" (Biggs, 2009, p. 100). It may also be valuable to offer cross-subsidies between multiple energy sectors. For instance, "the petroleum and electricity sectors can subsidise the modernisation and efficient use of domestic biomass fuels" (Biggs, 2009, p. 100).

Financing Options for the Verified Business Models

Based on the research conducted for the SBA Deliverable 10.5 on existing financing schemes in Botswana, South Africa, and Namibia, formal financial service providers (such as banks, government institutions, and financial technologies) were found to operate solely with enterprises meeting strict prerequisites. Often, businesses are expected to have a high annual turnover, documented financial records, and a minimum number of years in operation. MSMEs, the focus of the SteamBioAfrica project, are predominantly micro-entrepreneurs unable to meet such criteria (SBA D10.5).

Given the challenges in the African bioenergy market, particularly the difficulty project developers face in accessing financing, the types of required funding can be mapped across the early-stage business development cycle (refer to D10.5 on Innovative MSME Financing Toolbox). For the SBA solid biofuel, the start-up and growth phases are most relevant, covering the increase in the product's market presence and financing further growth and long-term operation (Hofmann & Khatun, 2013). Useful tools for financing the business models outlined in this report include:

- Simplification and shortening of application procedures for financing.
- Provision of microcredit, particularly for small-scale initiatives.
- Offering low-interest capital through targeted renewable energy funds and facilities, in cooperation with international financial institutions (IFIs) and potentially with donor support.
- More lenient loan prerequisites and insurance schemes for projects (Hofmann & Khatun, 2013, p. 366).

The SBA Deliverable 10.5 identified several alternative financing and investment options for MSMEs, including but not limited to:

- **Asset-based finance:** Enables companies to monetise the value of specific assets and access working capital under more flexible terms than conventional lending channels.
- **Factoring:** Where enterprises sell their creditworthy accounts at a discount (generally equal to interest plus service fees) and receive immediate cash from a specialised institution, or factor.

Recommendations

The primary objective of this report was to validate business models (BMs) identified in the SBA D9.3 report and, based on this validation, to propose sustainable and viable business models suitable for MSMEs, particularly those in the downstream of the biomass value chains in Southern Africa. This report recommends **four business models** from D9.3 for the commercialisation of the SBA solid biofuel: cash and carry, product bundling, distributor, and e-commerce models.

- **Cash and Carry:** Allows customers to purchase the solid biofuel directly from sellers, suitable for both formal businesses (retailers, gas stations) and informal businesses (roadside vendors, kiosks), with or without offering delivery services.
- **Product Bundling:** Combines the solid biofuel with complementary products (e.g., cookstoves, firewood/charcoal) to offer added value and convenience, applicable for large retailers as well as smaller vendors with financial capacity.
- **Distributor Model:** Utilises intermediaries to transport and distribute the solid biofuel to retail outlets, institutions, and end-users, leveraging networks for market reach and scalability.
- **E-commerce Model:** Sells the solid biofuel directly to consumers via online platforms, offering convenience and accessibility with included delivery services.

The first three business models were tested and verified during the SBA biofuel sales trials. It was determined that these three models are the most suitable for biomass MSMEs to commercialise the solid biofuel in the downstream of local value chains. This report recommends a fourth business model, the e-commerce model, for future consideration. As digital technologies advance and businesses increasingly embrace virtual spaces to offer their products and services globally, the SBA project sees a significant opportunity for biomass MSMEs to market the solid biofuel using these online channels. These four business models are essential for advancing the commercialisation of SBA solid biofuel and ensuring its availability in the market.

Categorisation and Evaluation of Business Models:

Business models (BMs) were categorised into two distinct groups:

- a) BMs targeting formal businesses such as retailers and gas stations.

b) BMs focusing on informal small-scale sellers like kiosks and roadside vendors.

A SWOT analysis was conducted to assess each BM category's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, providing a comprehensive evaluation framework for MSMEs interested in participating in solid biofuel commercialisation in the future.

Strategic Partnerships Essential for Solid Biofuel Commercialisation:

Collaboration with different actors in the value chain—wholesalers, retailers, and small businesses—is particularly important for the commercialisation of SBA solid biofuel.

Competitiveness and SBA Solid Biofuel Enhancement:

The sales trial highlighted the need for product optimisation (addressed under WP5) to enhance product competitiveness. Specifically, increasing the size of biofuel pieces and extending their burn time emerged as crucial improvement areas to align with market expectations and compete effectively with more established fuels like firewood and charcoal. This adjustment is pivotal in meeting consumer preferences for product efficiency and performance.

Packaging Centres and Distributors:

As the SHS technology becomes replicable across Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa, and the SBA solid biofuel becomes more accessible in the market, product distribution could involve packaging centres and distributors that supply wholesalers and large retailers. SBA project partners such as N-Big, CCF, and Carbon Capital in Namibia, and Ekasi in South Africa, could play a key role in facilitating the solid biofuel distribution.

Future outlook

Further market trials in Botswana and Namibia over a longer duration, particularly with an optimised SBA solid biofuel, are crucial to validate and improve the performance and acceptance of the solid biofuel. Additional sales trials will yield valuable data to refine business models, pricing strategies, and operational approaches, especially for sellers. A further market trial should also be conducted in South Africa.

Continued optimisation of SHS technology and the SBA solid biofuel is essential to demonstrate the full benefits and unique characteristics of solid biofuel, such as hydrophobic properties, longer burning duration, higher heat emission, and a slow burning process. An optimised SHS process will ensure the production of a solid biofuel that offers several superior qualities beyond those demonstrated during the sales trials, further strengthening the business models. While the trials highlighted the smokeless nature of the biofuel and its ease of handling and storage, other key aspects crucial for business models were not yet demonstrated.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036401.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

